

Non-Invasive Insulin Delivery System: A Review on Afrezza Inhaler Used In Diabetes Mellitus

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Abstract

Diabetes mellitus is the chronic pathogenic condition which is primarily due to inadequate insulin secretion and is responsible for major healthcare problems worldwide. Diabetes complication includes both micro vascular and macro vascular disease, both of which are affected by optimal diabetes control. Many individuals with diabetes rely on subcutaneous insulin administration by injection or continuous infusion to control glucose levels. Novel routes of insulin administration are an area of interest in the diabetes field, given that insulin injection therapy is burden for many patients. This review will discuss pulmonary delivery of insulin via inhalation specifically Afrezza, which represents a novel prandial insulin delivery method. This review discusses about Afrezza which is also a rapid acting oral inhalation insulin administered at the beginning of each meal. The U.S Food and Drug Administration has approved Afrezza (insulin human) inhalation powder, a rapid-acting inhaled insulin to improve glycemic control in adults (greater than or equal to 18 years) of age with Type 1 or Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T1DM or T2DM). The development of such insulin delivery technologies that are better tailored to patients' needs may improve patient compliance there by facilitating the attainment of treatment targets. The review summarizes the studies available and discusses the potential implication to patients to needle-free insulin administration.

Introduction

Diabetes is a severe chronic disease that arises when insulin generation is insufficient, or the generated insulin cannot be used in the body, resulting in a long-term metabolic disorder. It is the most common endocrine disorder. The number of people with diabetes worldwide has more than doubled during the past 20 years. One of the most worrying features of this rapid increase is the emergence of type 2 diabetes in children, adolescents, and young adults. The risk factors of type 2 diabetes are genetic factors, lifestyle, and behavioral risk factors and the exact cause of type-1 diabetes is unknown, but it is thought to be a combination of genetics and environmental factors. Diabetes affects an estimated 537 million adults worldwide between the age of 20 to 79. By 2030 643 million people will have diabetes globally, increasing to 783 million by 2045.

With the need for a more convenient and less invasive method of administration, researchers investigated alternate routes of insulin delivery. These routes included buccal, transdermal, oral, ocular, nasal, rectal, vaginal, uterine, and pulmonary delivery systems. These proposed routes often suffered from poor bioavailability. The epithelium is functionally impermeable to the large insulin molecule. Insulin, being a peptide hormone, begins to break down on contact with gastric peptidases

when ingested orally. Of all the alternative routes, pulmonary drug delivery showed the most promise.

The lung is highly vascularized with an approximate surface area of 130 m², or about the size of a tennis court. The large surface area affords rapid absorption and onset of action. This, along with the general lack of gastric peptidases within the lung, makes it an attractive target drug delivery. Compared with the nasal, rectal, buccal, and Conjunctiva routes, pulmonary delivery of insulin had an approximate 4 to 40 times increase in bioavailability.

Afrezza

In June 2014, the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) approved a new formulation of the Afrezza inhaled insulin powder to act as prandial insulin requirements for non-smoking adults with diabetes who are free of pulmonary disease. The new drug-device product became available for clinical use in the United States in February 2015. The Afrezza device consists of a dry powder inhaler (DPI) and a new dry powder formulation of recombinant regular human insulin (Technosphere insulin), which is packaged in a pre-filled cartridge and delivered through a hand held pocket-sized device. Technosphere insulin (TI) is dry powder recombinant human insulin. This system was developed in collaboration between Mankind Corp., by developing the recombinant human insulin powder, and Pharmaceutical Discovery Corp., who developed the Med Tone DPI device.

Formulation

The excipients in Afrezza inhaled insulin are Fumaryl diketopiperazine (FDKP) and polysorbate 80

- Fumaryl diketopiperazine (FDKP)-
Inert excipients that forms micro particles around the recombinant human insulin in Afrezza. The micro particles are the right size to be delivered into the lungs.
- Polysorbate80-
An inactive ingredient in Afrezza . Afrezza used Technosphere technology to deliver the insulin to the lungs. It is a drug and device combination that includes the insulin powder an inhaler, and cartridges containing the powder the insulin are absorbed into the bloodstream through the lungs in less than a minute. And blood sugar levels start to drops after about 12 minutes.

Delivery System of Afrezza

➤ Afrezza Cartridges

Afrezza consists of single-use plastic cartridges filled with a white powder containing insulin (human), which is administered via oral inhalation using the Afrezza Inhaler only.

Afrezza cartridges contain human insulin produced by recombinant DNA technology utilizing a non-pathogenic laboratory strain of *Escherichia coli* (K12). Chemically, human insulin has the empirical formula C₂₅₇H₃₈₃N₆₅O₇₇S₆ and a molecular weight of 5808. Afrezza inhalation Powder is a dry powder supplied as 4 unit or 8 unit cartridges. The 4 unit cartridge contains 0.35 mg of insulin. The 8 unit cartridge contains 0.7 mg of insulin.

➤ Afrezza Inhaler

The Afrezza Inhaler is breath-powered by the patient. When the patient inhales through the device, the powder is aerosolized and delivered to the lung. The amount of Afrezza delivered to the lung will depend on individual patient factors.

Fig 1-Afrezza Device

➤ Delivery System

- Afrezza comes in 2 strengths
 - 4 units (Blue cartridge)
 - 8 units (Green cartridge)
- If your prescribed Afrezza dose is higher than 8 units, you will need to use more than 1 cartridge.
- If you need to use more than 1 cartridge for your dose, throw away the used cartridge before getting a new one. You can tell when a cartridge has been used, because the cup has moved to the center.
- The Afrezza inhaler opens the cartridge automatically during use.
- Afrezza cartridges should only be used with the Afrezza Inhaler.
- Use only 1 Afrezza inhaler at a time. The same inhaler should be used for the 4 Unit or 8 unit cartridges.
- Throw away your Afrezza inhaler after 15 days and get a new one.

Injected Mealtyme Insulin Dose	AFREZZA® Dose	# of 4 unit (blue) cartridges needed	# of 8 unit (green) cartridges needed
up to 4 units	4 units		
5-8 units	8 units		
9-12 units	12 units		
13-16 units	16 units		
17-20 units	20 units		
21-24 units	24 units		

Table-Doses of Afrezza in units

Mechanism of action

Afrezza is a rapid acting inhaled insulin powder. When the insulin is inhaled through the device, the powder is aerosolized and delivered to the lung. Insulin lowers blood glucose levels by stimulating peripheral glucose uptake by skeletal muscle and fat and by inhibiting hepatic glucose production.

Pharmacodynamics

The pharmacodynamics profile for orally inhaled Afrezza 8 units relative to subcutaneously administered insulin lispro 8 units from a study in 12 patients with type 1 diabetes. The median time to maximum effect of Afrezza (measured by the peak rate of glucose infusion) was approximately 53 minutes (standard deviation of 74 minutes) and the effect then declined to near baseline levels by about 160 minutes.

Pharmacokinetics

The insulin contained in Afrezza is regular human insulin. Following pulmonary absorption into systemic circulation, the metabolism and elimination are comparable to regular human insulin.

- Absorption: The pharmacokinetic profiles for orally inhaled AFREZZA 8 units relative to subcutaneously administered insulin lispro 8 units from a study in 12 patients with type 1 diabetes are. The maximum serum insulin concentration was reached by 12-15 minutes after inhalation of Afrezza 8 units and serum insulin concentrations declined to baseline by approximately 180 minutes.
- Disposition: Systemic insulin disposition (median terminal half-life) following oral inhalation of Afrezza 4 and 32 units was 28-39 minutes, and 145 minutes for subcutaneous regular human insulin 15 units.

Indications and usage

Afrezza is rapid acting inhaled insulin indicated to improve glycemic control in adult Patients with diabetes mellitus.

Limitations of use

- Afrezza is not a substitute for long-acting insulin. Afrezza must be used in combination with long-acting insulin in patients with type 1 diabetes mellitus.

- Afrezza is not recommended for the treatment of diabetic ketoacidosis.
- The safety and efficacy of Afrezza in patients who smoke has not been established. The use of Afrezza is not recommended in patients who smoke or who have recently stopped smoking.

Route of Administration

Afrezza should only be administered via oral inhalation using the Afrezza Inhaler. Afrezza is administered using a single inhalation per cartridge.

Advantage-

1. Afrezza is rapid- acting insulin that's taken with an inhaler, so you don't need to inject it.
2. Afrezza start lowering blood sugar in about 12 minutes similar to the body's natural insulin response.
3. Afrezza is an alternative for people who experience skin reaction at injection site.

Fig 2– Afrezza Cartridge

Contraindications: Afrezza is contraindicated in patients with the following:

- During episodes of Hypoglycemia
- Chronic lung disease, such as asthma or chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), because of the risk of Acute Bronchospasm.
- Hypersensitivity to regular human insulin or any of the Afrezza excipients.

Warning

- Acute bronchospasm has been observed in patients with asthma and COPD using AFREZZA.
- AFREZZA is contraindicated in patients with chronic lung diseases such as asthmaCOPD .
- Before initiating AFREZZA, perform a detailed medical history, physical examination, to identify potential lung disease in all patients.

Adverse reactions

- Acute bronchospasm in patients with chronic lung disease.
- Hypoglycemia
- Decline in pulmonary function
- Lung cancer
- Diabetic ketoacidosis
- Hypersensitivity reactions

Storage

- Not in Use: Refrigerated Storage 2-8°C (36-46°F)
If a foil package is not refrigerated , the contents must be used within 10 days.
- In Use: Room Temperature Storage 25°C (77°F), excursions permitted 15-30°C (59- 86°F)

Handling: Before use, cartridges should be at room temperature for 10 minutes

Comparison between insulin inhalers vs. subcutaneous injections

Insulin inhaler and injections are both used to treat diabetes by lowering blood sugar levels, but they differ in how they are administered, how quickly they work, and how long they last in body.

1. Administration

Inhaled insulin is a powder that's inhaled through a special device, while insulin injections are delivered through a syringe.

2. Speed

Inhaled insulin starts working faster than injection insulin because it's adsorbed into the blood stream through the lung.

3. Duration

Inhaled insulin leaves the body more quickly than injected insulin. Usually within 1.5-3hours

4. Comfort

Inhaled insulin is a needle-free option that can be more comfortable for people who find injections painful or inconvenient.

5. Patient satisfaction

Patients are often satisfied with Exubera, and it can increase the acceptance of insulin therapy.

Conclusion

Diabetes is a significant world- wide health problem. The ultimate of for the treatment of DM should either be transplantation of some kind of β cells of pancreas or by correction of some genetic sequences. Emphasis must be given to prevent orderly the disease which may be related to lifestyle modifications. The traditional insulin therapy involves multiple daily subcutaneous injections which is really a heavy burden on patients and has prompted interest in developing alternative method for delivering insulin. The novel inhalation insulin therapy having more efficacies. insulin delivered through the lungs offers more than just a promising treatment of diabetes mellitus .Insulin has fast onset of action which should lead to improve both types 1 and type 2 DM. Inhaled insulin is effective than the traditional regimen of subcutaneous insulin or oral-glucose lowering medication .The key advantages of this novel medication are its non- invasive mode of delivery and its enhanced metabolic regulation. Inhaled insulin take effect quickly, it is useful for controlling post-meal glucose rise. it also provide a needle free option which is especially helpful for adult patients .To ensure the efficient use of insulin inhaler there view underlines the significance of patient education, particularly regarding appropriate inhaling techniques and dose to be used.

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